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Deliverable 3.3

Code for stochastic parameterizations to generate ensembles in 1D or 3D MFC configurations

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1. Introduction

A key objective of SEAMLESS is to develop innovative open-source-based generation and assimilation methods to accelerate the transition of the physical and biological components of CMEMS Monitoring and Forecasting Centres (MFCs) to probabilistic systems, with a better ability to deliver products with faithful associated uncertainties.

The scope of this document is to introduce Deliverable 3.3 (D3.3, Type: Code), which contains the codes of stochastic processes developed as part of Task 3.1 of WP3. The D3.3 codes are delivered to the SEAMLESS stakeholders in open-access repositories with public links provided in this document. These codes are used to generate ensembles with NEMO and HYCOM, which are the building blocks of all CMEMS modelling systems. Task 3.1 aims at transforming the traditional deterministic coupled physical-BGC modelling systems (i.e., one single initial state as input and one single final state as output) used by the CMEMS MFCs into numerically efficient probabilistic modelling systems (i.e., one initial pdf as input and one final pdf as output) performing ensemble simulations.

In the next section, we provide a brief description of the 2 coupled stochastic modelling systems considered in Task 3.1 including access to the software packages. The model systems are delivered at mid-term of WP3, to be available for the project's needs in the different work packages. The coupled NEMO-PISCES and HYCOM-ECOSMO probabilistic systems are delivered in the configuration used operationally in the Global (GLO) and Arctic (ARC) MFCs. The packages contain generic routines that can be transitioned in other operational systems, in 1D or 3D configurations.

A detailed presentation of the developments and applications of the model codes undertaken in SEAMLESS will be provided in the Deliverable 3.4 (Type: Report) upon completion of WP3.

2. Probabilistic ocean modelling systems

The conventional deterministic models are transformed into probabilistic systems by introducing stochastic processes to simulate different types of uncertainty sources in the systems (e.g., intrinsic model parameters, unresolved processes, external forcing). As a result of stochasticity, two different runs based on identical initial conditions eventually produce different trajectories in the state space. In this way, ensembles can be generated.

While the probabilistic version of NEMO was already existing to simulate ocean-ice dynamics (Bessières *et al.*, 2017), the stochastic coupled NEMO-PISCES version has been developed in the global setup implemented by the GLO MFC system (version r4.0-HEAD.r13720, provided by Mercator Ocean International) as part of Task 3.1. The resulting probabilistic code is available here: <https://zenodo.org/record/6303007>. It relies on independent Gaussian autoregressive processes as described in Brankart *et al.* (2015). The stochastic processes simulate a variety of uncertainty sources such as uncertain biological model parameters (as proposed by Garnier *et al.*, 2016), unresolved sub-grid scale processes and location uncertainties. The stochastic routines can be easily used to simulate uncertainties in physical model parameterizations, external forcing, or even initial conditions (Leroux *et al.*, 2022).

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The probabilistic formulation of HYCOM-ECOSMO relies on a method for generating two-dimensional pseudo random fields with a specific mean, variance, and co-variance as described in Evensen (1994). The code can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/record/5606973#.YeVsMmDTVqs>. The routines for creating perturbations in 3D (x,y,z) or 2D (x,y,t) are described here: https://github.com/lbertino/Random_2D_perturbations. In its seminal formulation, the stochastic fields are created to generate perturbations of the HYCOM layer thicknesses and ice thickness. The coupled HYCOM-ECOSMO system also includes external forcing perturbations both in physical and BGC components, and parameter perturbations in BGC component. Work is ongoing to extend this capability to physical model parameters as planned in Task 3.3.

Feedback from users will be useful to enrich the tools during the project, or to broaden the list of potential applications. Users are invited to send their comments and suggestions to the authors, in the prospect of future releases.

3. References

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